

Filling in the Gaps: Classification of Generically Coded GP Notes on Belonging to a Phenotype (A Case Study on Depression)

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Introduction

When searching patient history for specific conditions or traits (phenotypes), Read codes help identify relevant encounters. Some codes directly match the condition, while others cover unrelated conditions or are coded as generic in-person and phone consultations. Free text notes within generic records may provide useful context. Manual review is impractical. Machine learning models could classify generic encounters based on the free text and fill the gaps in the patient record (Figure 1). To develop such a model, labelled data is required. This study explores the potential of using predictions from a Large Language Model (LLM) as training labels with a focus on depression but this could be applied to other phenotypes.

Figure 1. A patient timeline with a focus on depression and generic undercoded encounters which need to be classified as (ir)relevant to depression.

Methods and Data

After being granted exceptional approval by NHS Lothian, we analysed patient records from Lothian GP practices, focusing on patients with at least one depression-related Read code. Retrieved free-text records were categorized into superlabels as *positive* (relevant), *neutral* (generic), or *negative* (unrelated). An LLM (Llama 3.1 [1]) reclassified 500 records from each category as *relevant*, *maybe relevant*, or *irrelevant*, based only on free text (reclassification set). Predictions were compared against the original Read-code classifications and discrepancies analysed to inform prompt engineering. The prompt was designed to produce ternary classification with a focus on high recall (the *maybe* class intended to be post-processed as *relevant*), while marking records with insufficient information (e.g., purely numeric) as *irrelevant*. We further compared the model's predictions to categories assigned by a GP to an evaluation set of 100 records. The evaluation set was randomly sampled uniformly across combinations of Read-code superlabels and labels predicted by the LLM in the reclassification set. The number of *negatives* is slightly smaller than *positives* and *neutrals* as the LLM always predicted *negatives* to be *irrelevant*. This distribution does not correspond to the proportions of population of *positives*, *negatives*, and *neutrals* in the data – it was chosen

for expert evaluation and commentary on all combinations appearing in the predictions and data. A GP (co-author SM) performed binary (*relevant/irrelevant*) and ternary (*relevant/maybe/irrelevant*) classification on the evaluation set based solely on the text.

Results

The comparison between GP, LLM predictions, and original Read code-derived superlabels is presented in Figure 2. The GP identified several notes as *insufficient* for classification. Most of these related to specifically labelled (*positive/negative*) notes rather than *neutrals* (Fig. 2a). The GP was more likely to classify a record as *relevant* or *irrelevant* rather than *maybe* (Fig. 2a). This outcome in combination with the LLM's high tendency to assign the *maybe* class (Figs 2b and 2c), and our intent to include or exclude *maybes* from the timeline led us to binarising the ternary LLM predictions. While the LLM's *maybes* do not perfectly align with the GP's *positive* predictions, they are more likely to match with *relevant* or *maybe* than *irrelevant*.

Figure 2. Confusion Matrices between (a) Read code and GP on all notes, (b) LLM predictions and GP on all notes, and (c) LLM predictions and GP on only neutral notes.

We have further investigated the Precision, Recall and F1 scores of identifying depression-related records in a variety of situations with the *insufficient* records removed (Table 1). If sufficient information is provided, the GP aligns well with the Read codes on the *positives* and *negatives*. The best alignment between the GP and the LLM is achieved through using the GP's binary prediction (*maybes* not allowed) and converting the LLM's *maybes* into *positives*.

Table 1. Accuracy results (without *Insufficients*)

Setting (gold vs prediction)	P	R	F1
Specified Read code (Binary) vs GP (Binary) (agreement between GP and code)	0.964	0.964	0.964
GP (Ternary) vs LLM (Ternary)	0.931	0.563	0.701
GP (Binary) vs LLM (Binary, Maybes Irrelevant)	0.966	0.538	0.691
GP (Binary) vs LLM (Binary, Maybes Relevant)	0.875	0.942	0.907

Conclusion

Based on our comparison between Read codes and the GP's performance on text only, we conclude that if the text is insufficient for such classification, it is far more likely to be associated with a specific (*positive/negative*) code, than a neutral one. The LLM's predictions aligned best with the GP (ignoring irrelevants) when the GP prediction was binary and the LLM's was binarised by converting maybes into relevants. This resulted in high recall, with slightly lower precision. In future work we intend to compare the performance of multiple GPs and use the LLM's output as silver standard for training local models for classification of neutral notes as relevant or irrelevant to depression. Our method and the suggested future work could be applied to other conditions to provide more complete timelines.

Study context

This study has been conducted as part of the AMBER (Antidepressant Medications: Biology, Exposure & Response) [2] project funded by a Wellcome Trust Mental Health Award. This work uses data collected by the NHS as part of their provision of patient care and support. Following exceptional approval by NHS Lothian, the analysis was completed on an extract of patient data in a Secure Data Environment managed by the DataLoch service: a partnership of the University of Edinburgh and NHS Lothian. One goal of the overall programme of work is to develop a scalable process for DataLoch in which clinical free-text can be de-identified for potential use within approved research projects. The data used for our development project cannot be requested in its raw form.

References

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